

ROLE OF PHILATELIA IN POPULARIZATION HISTORICAL AND PUBLIC MEMORY

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ABSTRACT

Role of postage issues as a visual component in the formation of the historical memory of the Ukrainian people is considered. The experience of the Ukrainian postal administrator "Ukrposhta" in stimulating interest in philately, enhancing the use of postal issues for advertising and promoting regional attractions, which reflects the historical and cultural heritage, is presented

Cultural heritage plays an important role in the formation of the historical memory and national consciousness of the people. The visual component possessed by post miniatures dedicated to monumental monuments, memorable places and events creates an information space that not only reflects the historical past, but also actively forms public memory.

Even in the era of globalization, it is not possible to erase national and cultural boundaries between states, and moreover, the presence of its own unique image, both for countries and for a particular region, acquires special significance.

Each region of Ukraine has historically developed a certain, characteristic and recognizable image. However, it is necessary to position, and thereby to popularize, this image, including taking into account the modern norms and rules of marketing theories and practices.

One of these methods is the form of collecting as philately, and the issue of postage stamps at the state level as an element of monetization.

2. Methods:

The article presents an analysis of the state policy on the formation of the historical memory of the Ukrainian people using the example of a separate region. The formation of thematic plans for the issue of postage stamps, the reconstruction of historical events creates a visual-figurative nature of a certain process, a sense of the personal involvement of each participant (Ukrposhta employee, philatelist-collector, local historian, etc.) to specific events, and personalities of national and world history.

3. Research results:

Donetsk region, according to academician B. Paton, is the pearl of Ukraine. However, for a long time the image of this beautiful land was associated only

with its industrial power. In the minds of many people, both in Ukraine and abroad, it was a large industrial zone with waste heaps, mines and factories. The modern Donetsk region is a scientific, cultural, sports center of our state and is gaining more and more attractiveness as a center of tourism. A large role in the formation of the new image was played by the purposeful work carried out by the local authorities of the region to popularize it in parallel with active environmental protection, restoration of existing and creation of new protected areas, historical and natural monuments, active improvement of cities and settlements.

One of the tools that can be used for effective positioning are postage issues - stamps, envelopes, cards. It should be noted that the stamp and the envelope are not only postal attributes that are necessary to pay for the postage of written correspondence, they are a kind of visiting card of the country, which forms a positive image of the state and its regions. Artistic plots depicted on postal issues carry information about the region, its history, achievements of science and culture, tourist attractions, acquaint with famous personalities who glorified this region.

The modern Ukrainian brand is still a little over thirty years old. And during this period, the postal administrator of Ukraine has already issued more than two thousand stamps (the number of subjects, excluding circulation, up to seventy-five subjects are issued per year), hundreds of subjects of envelopes and cards. Among them, the plots dedicated to the Donetsk region occupy an important place.

When preparing proposals that are sent for the formation of thematic plans for

the issue of stamps and other signs of postage, the administration staff carry out a lot of research work, use the recommendations of leading experts in local history, tourism business, philatelists-analysts of the Association of Philatelists of Ukraine.

Based on the study of archival materials, popular science and literary and artistic materials, a strategy was developed to promote the image of the Donetsk region through postal issues. Together with philatelists-collectors, work is underway to form reference books and collections of postage issues of modern Ukraine, as well as issues from the times of the USSR, and, of course, issues of other countries with a theme dedicated to this region.

The history of Donetsk deserves attention and comprehensive study. The city is a little over one hundred and fifty years old. Perhaps, in the history of Ukraine, this is a unique example of the formation and development of a city, which in one century has gone from a simple working village to a city with a modern European level of development. The settlement was created by the English industrialist John Hughes among the Azov steppe in 1869 from scattered villages and mines, and in 1917 it received city status, from 1924 - the city of Stalino, in 1961 it was renamed as Donetsk.

The first envelope dedicated to Donetsk was issued by the Ministry of Communications of the USSR on October 24, 1960. The building of the Opera and Ballet Theater was depicted on the envelope. It should be noted that the image of the theater has repeatedly been the subject for the release of envelopes; they were published in 1979, 1981, 1983, and 2001.

The theater is associated with the work of outstanding artists - Nikolai Bogolyubov, Olga Kovaleva, Anatoly Solovyanenko, Vadim Pisarev, Inna Dorofeeva and many others.

During the former Soviet Union, the famous symbols of the mining capital were depicted on postal envelopes - architectural monuments, a railway station, an airport, hotels, metallurgical plants of Donetsk, Mariupol, Yenakiyev, an engineering plant in Kramatorsk, large mines, as well as palaces of culture, sports and recreation facilities, educational institutions, picturesque corners of the area, etc. A series of envelopes dedicated to the anniversary dates of the formation of the cities of Gorlovka, Donetsk, Yasinovataya, Mariupol was issued. All these issues positioned Donbass as one of the largest industrial regions of the former USSR.

The modern life of the Donetsk region is characterized not only by the development of industry, but also full of cultural and sports events: creative exhibitions, sports competitions, festivals. "Prokofiev Spring", "Stars of the World Ballet", "Belcanto", "Golden Scythian", "Underwater Fantasies", festivals of children's creativity, chess tournaments, international competitions of pole athletes "Pole Stars", football tournaments - this is not a complete list of events held in the mining capital and already widely known abroad.

On May 26, 2000, within the framework of the Golden Scythian festival, a stamp and an envelope "Donetsk region" were issued. These were the first postal issues in independent Ukraine dedicated to the regions, which opened a new series of postage stamps in Ukraine "Our

Batktivshchyna". On the stamp against the background of the Donetsk landscape, the territory of the Donetsk region is schematically depicted on the map of Ukraine and the coat of arms of the Donetsk region. The coat of arms of the region and the inscription "Donetsk region" are depicted on the envelope in a yellow-blue frame. The continuation of the series took place in 2019 "Beauty and Greatness of Ukraine", where the stamp depicts "Holy Dormition Svyatogorskaya Lavra".

Both envelopes and stamps with stories about this region can rightfully be considered the hallmark of the region, since every day more than 100 thousand postal items from the region are scattered around the world, promoting and advertising Donetsk region through stories on the postal attributes. For example, only envelopes "Donetsk region" were sold through the network of post offices in the Donetsk region over a million copies. In addition, it should be noted that all labeled products that are published by the postal administrator of Ukraine are sold throughout the state through a network of post offices.

Balloons on envelopes (issued in 2001) appeared not by chance, firstly, the flights of bright colorful balloons in the Donetsk region accompany many actions and festivals. Secondly, Donetsk postal workers themselves became the authors of the bright show "Balloon Mail", the purpose of which is to popularize the history, achievements, prospects of the Donetsk region, the postal service, stimulate interest in collecting stamps, and develop philately.

The history of balloon mail is associated with extreme conditions, wars, natural phenomena. Modern flights of

balloons with mail on board in many countries of the world are of a propaganda nature, reminding contemporaries of the ingenuity of mankind, heroism and courage, and also advertising mail as the most important means of communication. Today balloon mail is only delivered on demonstration flights. It is interesting for philatelists not only in Ukraine, but also for collectors from countries such as Germany, Austria. The first unmarked envelope "Balloon Mail" was issued in Ukraine in 2001, then in 2002, and in 2003 a marked art envelope was dedicated to this event, in 2004, on World Post Day, the fifth flight of "Balloon Mail" will take place ... It has become traditional to hold this show in a picturesque place called Svyatogorye, the views of which are always adorned with envelopes, stamps, and postcards. Publications about these events were in the philatelic editions of Russia, England, and Germany.

The history of the development of postal services is also inseparable from the history of our region. In 2001, two remarkable anniversaries were celebrated: the centenary of the issue of zemstvo stamps of the Bakhmut district (formerly the city of Artemovsk, now Bakhmut) and the 130th anniversary of the zemstvo stamps of Mariupol. Several memorable postage issues were dedicated to these events. In the cities of Bakhmut and Mariupol, events were held that attracted public attention and had a great response, both in the regional and republican press. There were also responses to this event in specialized philatelic publications in Russia.

The glory of Donbass as a unique land was created by people and this is its main asset. This land attracted the attention

of such outstanding people as: chemist Dmitry Mendeleev, soil scientist Vasily Dokuchaev, poets Alexander Blok, Vladimir Mayakovsky, Marina Tsvetaeva, geologists Leonid Lutugin and Ivan Mushketov, artist Arkhip Kuindzhi and many other famous personalities. The names of our fellow countrymen, outstanding figures of science, art, sportsmen, are known far beyond the borders of Ukraine. With their scientific and creative achievements, high skill, sports records, they glorify Donbass, increase its authority in the state and in the world. These are generals, politicians and statesmen, scientists, poets and writers; domestic and foreign entrepreneurs and industrialists; composers, painters and artists; heroes of the first five-year plans and the Great Patriotic War; astronauts; Olympic champions and world record holders - postage issues of different times are dedicated to them:

- Arkhip Kuindzhi (1841-1910) - painter (USSR, 1991);
- Vladimir Nemirovich-Danchenko (1858-1943) - director, People's Artist of the USSR, writer, playwright, teacher (Ukraine, 2003);
- Mikhail Grishko (1901-1973) - Ukrainian singer (Ukraine, 2001);
- Pyotr Konchalovsky (1876-1956) - artist, painter (USSR, 1976);
- Sergei Prokofiev (1891-1953) - composer, pianist, conductor, People's Artist of the USSR (USSR, 1991);
- Viktor Yegorovich von Graff (1819-1867) - founder of the Velikoanadolsk forestry (Ukraine, 1993);
- Geogriy Sedov (1877-1914) - Russian hydrographer, polar explorer (Ukraine, 1997);

- Fedor Yenakiev (1852–1915) - a track engineer, founder of the Russian-Belgian Metallurgical Society, as well as the founder of the North Donetsk railway, the city of Yenakiyev was named in his honor (Ukraine, 2002);

- Nikita Izotov (1902–1951) - a miner at the Kochegarka mine (Gorlovka), an innovator in the coal industry (USSR, 1975);

- Alexey Stakhanov (1905/06–1977) - miner, pioneer of the mass movement of production innovators, hero of socialist labor (USSR, 1985);

- Peter Krivonos (1910-1980) - innovator of the Stakhanov movement in railway transport, hero of socialist labor (USSR, 1985);

- Pasha Angelina (1912 / 13-1959) - organizer of the first female tractor brigade in the USSR, twice a hero of socialist labor (USSR, 1985);

- Georgy Beregovoy (1921-1995) - pilot-cosmonaut (Ukraine, 1996, 2011).

The names of outstanding cultural figures, our compatriots and contemporaries are depicted on and on many other postage issues. In May 2002, within the framework of the Golden Scythian festival, at the opening ceremony of the monument to Anatoly Solovyanenko, two postage issues were presented - an artistic envelope and a block of postage stamps. Envelope from the series "People's Mystery of Ukraine", dedicated to Anatoly Solovyanenko - singer, lyric and dramatic tenor, People's Artist of Ukraine. A block of postage stamps from the thematic series "Works of monumental art (architectural monuments)", consisting of two stamps, one of which is dedicated to the Donetsk State Opera and Ballet Theater named after

Anatoly Solovyanenko. On the margins of the block there is a scene from the play "Don Quixote" with the participation of the soloists of the Donetsk Theater Vadim Pisarev and Inna Dorofeeva.

A special series of postal envelopes covers sporting events that took place in Donetsk: the IV European Athletics Championships among juniors (1977), the USSR Cup in Athletics (1986). Today Donetsk continues its glorious sports traditions. The whole world knows the names of the Olympic champions - the absolute champion of the XXVI Olympic Games Lilia Podkopayeva (organizer of the Golden Lily International Artistic Gymnastics Tournament); Olympic champion, 35-time pole vault record holder, organizer of the Pole Stars international festival Sergey Bubka. In 1992, an artistic unmarked envelope was issued dedicated to S. Bubka, the 1988 Olympic champion.

In 2002, the name of the sixteenth FIDE world chess champion Ruslan Ponomarev was immortalized on a stamp and envelope dedicated to the events of this chess tournament. Donetsk is also known as a city-organizer of events in the field of science, education and culture, not only at the regional level, but national and international. Expanding the circle of business partners, the region forms new relationships with many CIS and European countries.

Organization and holding of exhibitions of postage stamps from the collection of the Universal Postal Union in the regions of Ukraine is an effective element of the marketing communications complex. For several years, starting from 2004, collections of French and Polish stamps were exhibited in regional centers.

This action allowed the general public to see Poland and France presented in postage miniatures. In Donetsk, the exhibition was held during International Letter Week on the eve of World Post Day in October. Such actions allow one to learn more about the neighbors in the "European home", make it possible to compare and evaluate their achievements in the field of philately, to feel like a part of a single postal and information space.

4. Conclusions:

Over its more than one and a half century history, the postage stamp and the envelope have been reincarnated from

postage signs into full-fledged components of the material and spiritual culture of mankind. Significant events in the history of the state are marked by means of stamps; its cultural heritage is promoted. Therefore, postal administrations take a direct interest in the subjects depicted on postage stamps. Modern Ukrainian stamps have a high artistic level and, in terms of their content, are an excellent tool for advertising and promoting national symbols, form a positive attitude towards them both on the part of the population and on the part of domestic and foreign collectors.

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